

Investments in the Global Innovation Index

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In the following article, the variable "Investment" as indicated within the Global Innovation Index is analyzed. The Investment variable in the context of the Global Innovation Index (GII) refers to all resources dedicated by a country or a company to support and stimulate innovation. This concept includes various types of investments, such as those in human capital, research and development (R&D), infrastructure, technologies, and financial capital. The index measures a nation's ability to foster and sustain an environment conducive to innovation, evaluating not only the outcomes in terms of patents, new products, or services but also the extent of investment to create those outcomes. Investments are therefore both economic and institutional in nature, looking at the resources used to train people, improve the business environment, and facilitate access to funding for innovative initiatives. A crucial aspect is the role of the state and the private sector in investing in scientific research, emerging technologies, and professional training. A high level of investment in these areas is generally indicative of an innovation-oriented economy. In the GII, investment is also evaluated through indicators such as public and private R&D spending, education levels, technological infrastructure, and government policies aimed at promoting innovation. Greater investments in these sectors typically lead to improved conditions for innovation and, consequently, better performance in the global index. This framework helps to understand the direct link between investments and a nation's innovation capacity, which is essential for economic and social progress.

Investments in the Global Innovation Index in 2022. The data you provided reflects investments within the context of the 2022 Global Innovation Index (GII), an index that measures a country's innovation capabilities and the investments supporting innovation. Analyzing the data, we can observe significant diversity in terms of investments among countries, and we note that economic, political, and cultural factors play a crucial role in influencing how a country promotes and supports innovation. In this commentary, we will explore the implications of such differences, analyzing key factors that may explain variations in investment levels and the importance of innovation as a driver of economic growth and development. Among the countries at the top of the list, we find Iran (96.5), Estonia (96.2), and Singapore (92.5), which rank among the highest investors in innovation. This might seem surprising for some countries, particularly Iran, which is not commonly perceived as a technological innovation hub compared to countries like the United States or Israel. However, this position can be explained by the emphasis Iran has placed in recent years on scientific research, especially in science and technology, and the increasing focus on university education and training in STEM (Science, Technology, Engineering, and Mathematics) disciplines. This suggests that despite economic and political challenges, strong investment in innovation is seen as a strategic element for long-term development. Estonia is another interesting case study: this small country is often considered a "tech hub" thanks to its advanced digital infrastructure, a highly digitalized public sector, and government policies that encourage tech startups. Estonia has made digital innovation a national priority, and this is clearly reflected in its high investment levels. Singapore, known for its open and advanced economy, is a global center of innovation, with government policies aimed at incentivizing research and development in sectors such as biotechnology, digital finance, and green technology.

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The high level of investment in innovation aligns with its approach to growth and global competitiveness. Among traditionally advanced innovation countries, some, like the United States (76.3) and the United Kingdom (63.2), show investment levels that, while high, are lower than those of leading countries. In the United States, innovation is driven by the private sector, with tech giants like Google, Apple, and Microsoft dominating the technology landscape. However, the U.S. government tends to allocate fewer public resources toward innovation compared to other nations, such as Germany or Japan, where state subsidies and public-private collaborations are more prevalent. The United Kingdom is going through a period of uncertainty due to political factors like Brexit, which has impacted the economic climate and investments. Nevertheless, London remains a key center for technological innovation, especially in digital finance and biotechnology. However, political uncertainties may have limited the UK's ability to reach higher investment levels. Some of the more developed countries, such as Germany (25.4) and Japan (24.2), show relatively low investment levels compared to expectations. Both countries are known as global leaders in industrial production and advanced technology, and their low ranking on the list might suggest that, despite their strong economies, they may not be as strong in directly investing in innovation compared to other nations. However, it could also reflect the fact that these countries already have highly advanced infrastructure and systems, and therefore may not require the same level of innovation investments as emerging economies. On the other hand, some emerging countries, such as Mauritius (65.9), show surprising levels of investment in innovation relative to their global economic weight. Mauritius has sought to diversify its economy, traditionally based on agriculture and tourism, by investing in sectors such as finance, ICT (Information and Communication Technology), and education. This demonstrates how even relatively small countries can prioritize innovation as a means to accelerate economic growth. India (38.8), an emerging economic giant, has significantly improved its innovation investments in recent years, thanks to a growing ecosystem of tech startups and a strong focus on engineering and computer science. However, India still faces challenges related to social inequalities and access to quality education, factors that may limit the country's innovative potential. Countries like Vietnam (11.4) and the Philippines (10.6) are beginning to make strides in innovation, even though they are starting from a lower base. Both countries are trying to capitalize on their rapidly growing economies and young workforces, but they still need to invest significantly in infrastructure and education to fully exploit their potential. Finally, it is interesting to note that countries like Italy (6.4), Brazil (17.2), and Argentina (4.0), despite being medium or large economies, have very low investment levels in innovation. This could be indicative of structural economic challenges, a lack of effective government policies, or difficulties in implementing technological infrastructure. In the case of Italy, the country suffers from a chronic lack of investment in key sectors such as research and development, and although there are areas of excellence in specific sectors such as fashion, design, and mechanical production, the country as a whole struggles to keep pace with leading global players in terms of technological innovation. The analysis of the Global Innovation Index 2022 data clearly highlights the correlation between innovation investments and economic growth. Countries that have invested heavily in key sectors such as education, research and development, technological infrastructure, and startups tend to thrive in the modern global economy. However, countries with established economies but low innovation investments may see a decline in their competitiveness if they do not quickly adapt to these new global dynamics.

Investments in the Global Innovation Index from 2013 to 2022. The analysis of data related to investments in the Global Innovation Index (GII) for the period 2013-2022 reveals significant changes in investment levels and innovation performance in various countries. These data show an evolving global landscape, with some nations experiencing impressive improvements, while others have seen substantial declines in their commitment to innovation. In this detailed commentary, we will explore general trends, the successes and failures of certain countries, and reflect on the factors that have contributed to these variations. Among the countries that have recorded exceptional growth, Iran and

Estonia stand out in particular. Iran saw an extraordinary increase of 83.8 points in the GII, with a percentage rise of 659.84%. This improvement can be attributed to a significant increase in investments in research and development, as well as a focus on strategic sectors such as energy, materials science, and nuclear technologies. Despite international sanctions and economic difficulties, Iran has managed to find resources to enhance its innovation sector, particularly through scientific training initiatives and collaboration with universities and national research institutes. Estonia, which recorded an increase of 80.7 points (520.65%), is an excellent example of how a small country can become a global leader in technological innovation. Estonia has invested heavily in digitalization, developing advanced technological infrastructure and promoting digital transformation at the government and private sector levels. The Estonian "e-government" model and its focus on innovative digital solutions, such as e-residency, have allowed the country to emerge as a tech hub in Europe. Mauritius has also achieved notable results, with an increase of 38.3 points (138.77%). The island has sought to diversify its economy, traditionally based on tourism and sugar, by investing in emerging sectors such as finance, information technology, and biotechnology. This transformation was made possible by government policies favorable to innovation and the creation of a business-friendly environment that attracted foreign investments and supported local startups. Some countries, such as Israel, Singapore, and Saudi Arabia, recorded moderate but significant improvements. Israel, with an increase of 18.1 points (29.05%), remains a global leader in innovation, particularly in advanced technologies such as cybersecurity, artificial intelligence, and biotechnology. Despite relatively modest progress in percentage terms, Israel continues to be one of the most innovative countries in the world, thanks to a dynamic startup ecosystem and strong links between the private sector and academia. Singapore saw an improvement of 18.6 points (25.17%), further consolidating its position as one of the world's leading financial and technological hubs. The Singaporean government has continued to support innovation through skills development initiatives and tax incentives for research and development, further strengthening its role as a leader in innovation in Asia. Saudi Arabia has made strides with an increase of 8.2 points (23.98%), partly thanks to its Vision 2030 strategy, which aims to diversify the economy beyond the oil sector. Investments in sectors such as technology and renewable energy, along with social and economic reforms, have contributed to improving the innovation environment in the country. Among the countries that experienced a decline in their levels of innovation, we find some traditional leaders such as the United States, Canada, and the United Kingdom. The United States recorded a drop of 6.3 points (-7.63%), reflecting a relative stagnation in the context of a highly innovative economy. This could be due to a reduction in public investments in research and development, a recurring issue in recent years. Despite the decline, the United States remains one of the most innovative nations, thanks to the strength of its technology companies and universities. Canada also experienced a decline, with a decrease of 7.1 points (-9.45%). This decrease could be attributed to insufficient investments in key sectors such as technology and artificial intelligence, despite the country's strong innovation potential. A similar situation is observed in the United Kingdom, where the drop of 12.8 points (-16.84%) might be linked to economic and political uncertainty resulting from Brexit, which has affected foreign investments and international research collaborations. Some countries have recorded significant declines, with reductions exceeding 50%. Among these, Norway, Japan, and South Korea stand out, all countries known for their tradition of innovation. Norway saw a decrease of 29.9 points (-62.95%), a surprising decline for a country with a strong economy based on natural resources and advanced technologies. This could reflect a reduction in investments in non-oil sectors, in line with the energy transition the country is undergoing. Japan saw a drop of 25 points (-50.81%), signaling a potential crisis in technological innovation. Despite being a global leader in robotics and electronics, Japan has struggled to maintain its competitive edge in recent years. This decline could reflect an aging population and a lack of new policies to support startups and digital innovation. South Korea,

which recorded a drop of 47.8 points (-74.22%), is another surprising case, given its status as a global technology leader. Despite the presence of giants like Samsung and LG, the country may have experienced a decline due to market saturation and global competition in key sectors such as electronics and telecommunications. A significant group of developing countries, including Brazil, Mexico, and Argentina, has seen dramatic declines in innovation levels. Brazil recorded a decrease of 15.9 points (-48.04%), Mexico lost 16 points (-66.95%), and Argentina saw a drop of 13 points (-76.47%). These declines reflect a lack of investments in research and development, political and economic instability, and structural difficulties that limit innovation in these countries. Despite their potential in terms of human and natural resources, many Latin American countries continue to struggle to build ecosystems conducive to innovation. The analysis of Global Innovation Index data from 2013 to 2022 highlights the importance of consistent policies and sustained investments to promote innovation. Countries that have made the most progress, such as Iran, Estonia, and Mauritius, have been able to capitalize on opportunities arising from strategic investments and proactive government policies. In contrast, countries that have experienced declines, particularly traditionally innovative nations like the United States, South Korea, and Japan, will face significant challenges to remain competitive in an increasingly knowledge- and technology-based world.

Economic policies to promote investments in the Global Innovation Index. Economic policies aimed at promoting investments in the Global Innovation Index (GII) must address a range of global and national challenges, with a focus on infrastructure, human capital, public-private collaboration, financing, and a regulatory framework that fosters innovation. These policies are crucial for helping countries improve their position in the GII and, ultimately, stimulate economic growth, competitiveness, and resilience to crises. There are several economic levers that governments and institutions can adopt to encourage investments in innovation. One of the main areas to focus on is the improvement of technological infrastructure. Investments in telecommunications networks, transport systems, and digital connectivity are essential to supporting an innovative ecosystem. Digital infrastructure, in particular, forms the backbone for many innovative activities, enabling businesses to quickly access information, interact with clients and partners globally, and operate efficiently. Governments should promote policies to accelerate the deployment of high-speed broadband, 5G, and other advanced technologies, as well as encourage the adoption of cloud solutions and information technologies by businesses, especially small and medium enterprises (SMEs), which often struggle to access high-level technological resources. Additionally, countries should invest in sustainable energy infrastructure, necessary to power the growing energy needs of innovative sectors such as artificial intelligence, blockchain, and the Internet of Things. Beyond physical and digital infrastructure, it is crucial to invest in human capital. People are the primary resource for innovation, and economic policies must be designed to develop an educational and training ecosystem capable of responding to the needs of the labor market and innovative businesses. This means implementing policies to improve the level of education, with particular attention to STEM skills (Science, Technology, Engineering, and Mathematics), as well as promoting higher education and scientific research. Governments should facilitate access to education through scholarships, low-interest loans, and tax incentives for those investing in their own education or that of their employees. It is also necessary to create retraining programs for the existing workforce, ensuring that people can adapt to technological changes and new market demands. Another crucial aspect is attracting qualified foreign talent, encouraging international worker mobility, and creating favorable conditions for the immigration of experts in key innovation sectors. Fiscal policies represent another tool to stimulate innovation investments. Many countries use tax incentives to encourage companies to invest in research and development (R&D), such as tax credits, fiscal incentives for innovative startups, and deductions for investments in emerging technologies. These incentives can significantly reduce the

cost of innovation for businesses, encouraging more companies to engage in innovative projects. Furthermore, it is important to develop a tax system that rewards innovation success, for example, by reducing taxes for companies that create patents, new products, or innovative services. However, it is necessary to balance these incentives with sustainable fiscal policies that do not compromise public finances while ensuring a tax environment conducive to innovation. Another area to focus on is public-private collaboration. Public-private partnerships are essential for sharing risks and resources, accelerating the development of new technologies, and stimulating innovation in strategic sectors. Governments can promote the creation of innovation clusters, where universities, research centers, and companies collaborate to develop cutting-edge technologies. Such clusters can benefit from public funding for applied research and pre-competitive development projects, as well as shared infrastructure and services, such as laboratories and coworking spaces. Universities and research centers can play a crucial role in promoting innovation, not only through the production of new scientific knowledge but also by creating spin-offs and transferring technology to businesses. Financing innovation is a key aspect of economic policies aimed at promoting investments. Many innovative companies, especially in the early stages of development, face difficulties in accessing adequate financing due to the high risks associated with innovation. Governments can create or facilitate access to venture capital funds, loan guarantees, and subsidized financing programs for startups and innovative companies. Moreover, it is important to develop deeper and more accessible capital markets, where innovative companies can raise financial resources through the issuance of shares or bonds. Governments can also incentivize private investment in venture capital through tax breaks for investors who fund innovative companies. In some cases, governments can create sovereign or innovation-focused investment funds, which can provide capital to companies in high-potential technology sectors. A key aspect of economic policies is the creation of a regulatory framework conducive to innovation. Regulations must be designed to facilitate the development of new technologies and business models without imposing excessive bureaucratic burdens. An overly rigid regulatory environment can stifle innovation, particularly in emerging sectors such as biotechnology, renewable energy, and digital technologies. Governments must balance the need for regulation to ensure safety and consumer protection with the need to allow for experimentation and flexibility in launching new products and services. In some sectors, such as cryptocurrencies or autonomous driving, new experimental regulatory models, known as "sandbox" environments, have emerged. These allow companies to test new technologies in a simplified and controlled regulatory environment. This regulatory flexibility can accelerate the adoption of disruptive innovations and attract investments in high-growth sectors. An emerging area of great relevance for innovation is environmental policies. With the growing focus on sustainability and climate change, economic policies must promote innovation in green technologies, such as renewable energy, sustainable mobility, and energy efficiency technologies. Governments can promote environmental innovation through tax incentives for companies developing clean technologies, subsidies for research in the field of renewable energy, and regulations that stimulate the adoption of sustainable practices. Climate policies can become a powerful driver for innovation if designed correctly, contributing both to economic growth and environmental protection. Finally, it is important to emphasize the importance of a comprehensive and coherent national innovation strategy. Governments should develop long-term plans for innovation, setting clear and measurable goals, identifying strategic sectors, and allocating resources efficiently. These strategies must involve all key players in the innovation ecosystem, including universities, businesses, workers, and civil society. Only through coordinated and sustainable efforts will it be possible to promote an innovation-friendly environment and improve a country's position in the Global Innovation Index.

Conclusions. The value of investments has significantly decreased between 2013 and 2022, dropping from an average of 31.37 to a value of 19.19, equivalent to a reduction of 38.84%. However, there are countries where investment values have grown significantly, such as Iran with +659.84%, Estonia with +520.65%, Iceland with +170.95%, Mauritius with +138.77%, and Malta with +103.61%. There are also countries where investment values have decreased far beyond the average, such as Ukraine with -92.75%, Guatemala with -92.86%, Belarus with -95.91%, Algeria with -97.48%, and Ethiopia with -98.37%. Looking at the countries with the highest per capita income in 2022, there is a wide heterogeneity in investment levels, ranging from a value of 96.2 units in the case of Estonia to a value of 15.5 in the case of Austria. Therefore, it is not possible to conclude that investment levels alone are a decisive factor for economic growth and development.

Source: Global Innovation Index

Link: <https://www.wipo.int/web/global-innovation-index>

Country	2022	Country	2022	Country	2022
Iran, Islamic Rep.	96,5	Belgium	22,5	Namibia	7
Estonia	96,2	Uruguay	22,5	Cote d'Ivoire	6,4
Singapore	92,5	Rwanda	18,4	Italy	6,4
Israel	80,4	New Zealand	17,8	Ghana	6,2
United States	76,3	Norway	17,6	Burkina Faso	6,1
Canada	68	Brazil	17,2	Hungary	5,5
Hong Kong SAR, China	67,5	Korea, Rep.	16,6	Tajikistan	5,4
Mauritius	65,9	Malaysia	16,2	Czechia	5,3
United Kingdom	63,2	Austria	15,5	Myanmar	5,3
Switzerland	59	Indonesia	13,9	Tunisia	5,2
Sweden	49,3	Kenya	13,9	Zambia	5,2
Iceland	48,5	Bahrain	13,4	Albania	5
Luxembourg	42,8	Niger	13,3	Greece	5
Saudi Arabia	42,4	Croatia	13,2	Panama	5
France	39,9	Spain	12,8	Russian Federation	5

Malta	39,5	Chile	12,6	Bulgaria	4,9
India	38,8	Thailand	12,5	Trinidad and Tobago	4,8
Finland	38,5	Jamaica	11,7	Peru	4,7
Cyprus	38,2	Kuwait	11,4	Poland	4,6
United Arab Emirates	35,8	Vietnam	11,4	Mozambique	4,5
Lithuania	34,8	Latvia	10,7	El Salvador	4,2
Denmark	34,7	Philippines	10,6	Argentina	4
Netherlands	33,9	Qatar	10,6	Uganda	4
Montenegro	31,8	Colombia	10,5	Oman	3,9
South Africa	31,6	Portugal	10,1	Slovenia	3,9
China	28,7	Egypt, Arab Rep.	8,1	Honduras	3,7
Australia	28,3	Moldova	8,1	Botswana	3,6
Germany	25,4	Mexico	7,9	Pakistan	3,5
Jordan	25,4	Turkiye	7,9	Bangladesh	3,1
Senegal	25,4	Nigeria	7,8	Ecuador	3
Japan	24,2	Cambodia	7,5	Mali	3
Ireland	22,8	Morocco	7,2	Serbia	3

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